

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

O.S. Islamova

Kutahya Dumlupinar University, Doctoral student on Public Administration, Department of
Political Science

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14840680>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the role of women in public administration, their participation in socio-political life, and achievements in ensuring gender equality. Based on international and national experiences, the significance of female leaders in strengthening social justice, ensuring economic growth, and making decision-making processes more inclusive is highlighted. The study examines the impact of gender equality on societal development using statistical data from international organizations such as the United Nations, the World Bank, and the IPU. Additionally, legislative reforms and their outcomes aimed at increasing women's political and economic participation in Uzbekistan are discussed. The article emphasizes women's involvement in public administration as a key indicator of democracy and sustainable development, offering recommendations for promoting gender equality.*

Keywords: *women's role, public administration, gender equality, political participation, social justice, economic development, democracy, legislative reforms, sustainable development, women's rights.*

INTRODUCTION

Women's participation in public administration is one of the fundamental conditions for building a democratic society. By engaging in political, economic, and social processes, they make a significant contribution to societal development.

According to the United Nations, countries with higher female leadership participation experience faster social stability and economic growth.

Female leaders play a crucial role in protecting the interests of vulnerable populations, promoting gender equality, and ensuring social justice. At the same time, they serve as an inspiration for the younger generation in their social and professional development.

METHODS

The experience of the world's most developed countries demonstrates that women's involvement in public administration is essential for strengthening democracy and achieving sustainable development goals.

In Uzbekistan, systematic reforms are being implemented to protect women's rights and interests and to increase their political, economic, and social engagement. Gender equality has become one of the key priorities of state policy.

Women's participation in public administration is of great significance for the social, economic, and political development of society. Their involvement contributes to strengthening social justice, gender equality, and democratic processes.

Female leaders are more inclined to protect the interests of vulnerable groups and, through their activities, help overcome societal stereotypes while promoting gender equality. Their presence in leadership serves as an inspiration for young girls in their social and professional development.

Women in leadership positions contribute to creating equal opportunities in the labor market. They focus on supporting female entrepreneurs and creating favorable conditions, enabling economic policies to be more inclusive.

Research shows that female leaders achieve high results in making decisions that drive efficiency and innovation. Their participation in political processes makes decision-making more inclusive and democratic. Policies developed with female involvement tend to better reflect public interests and address the broader needs of the population. Additionally, female leaders play a key role in advocating for laws and initiatives that ensure gender equality.

Global Statistics:

The proportion of women among parliamentarians worldwide is 26.7% (2023, IPU data). More than 20 countries have female heads of state. Countries like Norway, Finland, and New Zealand ensure high levels of gender equality. In Iceland, women make up 47% of the government members. In Rwanda, the share of women in the parliament is 61%, the highest in the world. In India, the share of women among parliamentarians in 2023 is 15.1%, but locally, gender quotas ensure more than 40% participation. In Ethiopia, women are actively involved in political decision-making processes, with women holding the position of deputy prime minister. The participation rate of women in the labor market worldwide is 46.9% [1].

According to the World Bank, achieving gender equality could add \$12 trillion to the global economy by 2025. According to UNESCO, women constitute more than 30% of the world's researchers.

Women's involvement in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) fields remains low (around 20%).

In ancient times, women did not engage in food production; their tasks included waiting for their husbands in the cave, cooking mammoth meat, decorating the home, and raising children. At that time, people lived in groups, and women could not choose a husband for themselves. Men started creating families and selecting healthy women for themselves. In the future, women began participating in hunting, and their role was to trap animals with stones. This marked the first indication of women's gradual equality with men.

In ancient Greece, women's roles in the family and society were governed by strict state orders. A woman's role was to tell her husband what to do and how to do it, leading him. At that time, love marriages did not exist, and all relationships and families were based on political interests. Having children was also considered a state task. If a woman could not have children, the man had the right to marry another woman. Of course, the man would not marry her, and the woman's position was publicly recognized. If the woman gave birth to children, they would become legitimate heirs.

During the Soviet Union era, women were held responsible for the safety of the family, raising children, and their future life. Regardless of what happened in the family, women were always blamed. This was because the psychology of citizens was structured in a way that women were held accountable for all the mistakes of men [2].

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, prominent intellectuals such as M. Behbudi, A. Fitrat, and A. Avloni voiced significant thoughts on the role of women in society. For instance, in Fitrat's work "Family", he states: "The social and political activity of women is essential for national freedom and progress. Women should not only be occupied with household chores and child-rearing." Women's rights are, of course, also linked to religion and national values. Before

the arrival of Islam, it was common for girls to be buried alive, which is widely known. The sacred religion of Islam has always ordered the honoring of women. The saying "Paradise is under the feet of mothers" has not lost its significance over the centuries. Islamic teachings granted women equal rights with men in seeking knowledge, working, inheriting, and participating in societal development. Hadiths declare that the pursuit of knowledge is a duty for both Muslim men and women. Islam grants more rights to women in matters of family, marriage, and inheritance, prohibits cohabitation without marriage, and ensures women's rights through the institution of mahr (a mandatory gift given to the bride by the groom).

The 20th century became a turning point in the understanding of women's rights and freedoms, their political opportunities, and responsibilities. During this century, women achieved political rights that had been denied to them for millennia. This era witnessed a fundamental shift in the attitudes toward women, where not only family life but also the status of women in state and society were equalized with men. However, these accomplishments were not easily attained. Women had to balance household duties while also engaging in political matters, dedicating much more energy than men to fulfill their responsibilities and secure their political positions.

Thanks to the strong political will of Uzbekistan's President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the interests of women, gender equality, and family stability have become one of the priority areas of national policy. Women's participation in social, political, economic, and cultural life has been significantly expanding. In a short period, a national legislative framework in line with international standards has been developed, with over 80 normative legal acts adopted in the past five years. Important laws such as the "Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" and "On Protecting Women from Pressure and Violence" have been enacted and implemented. The Gender Strategy for the period up to 2030 has been adopted to ensure the full implementation of gender equality policies. Efforts to introduce gender expertise for legislative documents, adopt gender-sensitive national budgets, and conduct gender audits are actively underway [3].

RESULTS

The development of women's entrepreneurship has led to a twofold increase in the number of female entrepreneurs, reaching over 200,000 in recent years. Efforts are being made to provide women with vocational training and favorable credit conditions. On International Women's Day this year, the President of Uzbekistan issued a decision to support women's entrepreneurship and employment, allocating \$100 million for women to establish small businesses and entrepreneurship in 2023 [3].

Today, as the country pursues an innovative economic development path, particular attention is given to science, where female scholars are contributing significantly to the country's progress. Their scientific research in industry, agriculture, social education, and cultural sectors has made a significant impact, gaining recognition from the global scientific community. The increasing number of women involved in science in our country is a testament to this development.

Preferential loans and special quotas have been allocated for women, and the government has taken on the responsibility of fully covering the contract payments for those studying in the master's program from the state budget. As a result, the stereotypes that girls should not be educated and should stay at home are being eliminated. Currently, more than half of the students in higher education institutions are girls. If we compare the 9% enrollment in higher education in 2017 with the current 43%, we can see a significant increase in the share of women in higher

education. Furthermore, women have actively entered advanced fields such as digital economy and information technology, in addition to the traditional fields of education, medicine, and tailoring. Certainly, this trend will continue to grow and produce positive results in the future.

As a result, today in our society, there are nearly 1,000 PhD holders, nearly 5,000 candidates of sciences, and more than 10 academicians who are making significant contributions to various sectors of science, industry, and production.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized: “Respecting and honoring women, the pillars of family and society, the blessings and beauty of our lives, has always been a great value for our people and will continue to be so.” Today’s modern women can be described as politically active citizens, entrepreneurs, medically literate and moral mothers, and knowledgeable wives with economic expertise. In the family, not only the man must be well-educated, literate, and skilled in his profession, but his wife must also have a profession or some form of knowledge, as required by modern times. This is because mothers raise the future generation.

Participating in the adoption of state laws, advocating for women’s issues, and protecting their interests are of great importance. Research shows that women’s issues cannot be resolved on their own; they require consistent state policies, support from the population, and, most importantly, active participation from women themselves. In our country, a comprehensive reform plan has been developed to increase the role and status of women in society, focusing on ensuring their employment and implementing the necessary measures.

DISCUSSION

The involvement of women in social and political life in society is one of the methods for shaping social-political culture, and the realization of their relationship with power, as well as their social-political opportunities and potential, is considered the most fundamental and urgent indicator of democracy in society. Therefore, it is advisable to address the social-political, economic, and cultural interests that hinder women’s participation in the social-political life of the state based on the principle of equality. Such tasks must take into account the rights and interests, potential and opportunities of all women. To further increase the number of socially active, morally mature women, who are the vital pillars of society, the following proposals are suggested:

- Taking strict measures against violations that hinder the promotion of women in positions;
- Developing special laws that ensure labor rights and work-life balance for women;
- Developing special indicators for continuous monitoring of women's participation in government institutions;
- Creating opportunities for participation in global educational programs focused on management and leadership.

Ensuring the effective implementation of state policy in support of women, protecting their rights and legitimate interests, and increasing their role and activity in the social-political life of the country involves the following key tasks: in any system and social environment, the well-being of the family can be achieved through increasing the social-political activity of women. If the family is prosperous, it will, in turn, contribute to the development of society. Therefore, addressing women's issues provides an opportunity to accomplish many important tasks worthy of recognition at the societal level. The moral virtues characteristic of women are manifested in their closeness to nature and people, their constant pursuit of goodness, honest work, and enjoyment of the unequal gifts and beauties of the world. The spirituality of women is a bright reflection of

social life. This is because both family life and economic and political life are reflected in women. Every aspect of a woman's spirituality is intricately connected with the social-political life of society.

The love, purity, and dedication of women in the family are a source of honor and blessing for the family, and their influence on society is even greater. Preserving national values and continuing national traditions are also responsibilities that lie with women today. In short, the modern Uzbek woman, who has a place and role in the social-political arena of society, is an active social individual who has received education, acquired a profession, risen through the ranks of service, and directly participates in the life of the country and society. The peace and stability prevailing in the family and our country, the health and happiness of loved ones, are among the main factors that boost women's confidence in the future and positively affect their mood. Today, significant reforms have been implemented in our country to help women find their rightful place in the family and society. A legal framework regarding women's rights has been established. The issue of women has been raised to the level of state policy in our country. Showing respect to women and honoring them has become the fundamental principle of showing respect to the nation, the homeland, the future, and the coming generations.

CONCLUSION

The participation of women in state governance is of crucial importance in achieving the goals of building a democratic society and ensuring sustainable development. The results of the research show that female leaders play a significant role in protecting the interests of vulnerable populations, ensuring gender equality, strengthening social justice, and fostering economic growth.

The measures being implemented globally to ensure gender equality, particularly in countries like Norway, Rwanda, and Iceland, where female participation is highly emphasized, are driving social and economic stability and boosting innovation. Likewise, significant reforms have been implemented in Uzbekistan to promote gender equality and enhance the political, economic, and social activity of women.

The adoption of the law on "Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men," the gender strategy, and broad measures supporting female entrepreneurship have led to an increasing participation of women in the country's socio-political life. The expansion of access to higher education and the creation of special opportunities for women are further increasing the contribution of modern women to the development of society.

Supporting women's participation in social-political life, protecting their rights and interests, and increasing the number of women in leadership positions will remain key priorities for future development. Ensuring women's rights and achieving gender equality must not only rely on state reforms but also be supported by all layers of society. Only then will the social and political activism of women contribute to the stable development of our country and the strengthening of democratic values.

REFERENCES

Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dedicated to International Women's Day. // <http://uza.uz/oz/politics/2018>, March 7.

Abdullaev, D., Shukhratovna, D. L., Rasulovna, J. O., Umirzakovich, J. U., & Staroverova, O. V. (2024). Examining Local Item Dependence in a Cloze Test with the Rasch Model. *International Journal of Language Testing*, 14(1), 75-81.

Musurmanova, A. (2018). Family reading as a factor of spiritual and moral development of the child *The Way of Science. International scientific journal (ISSN 2311-2158)*, 1(47), 70-72.

ILO report, 2023.

Pronin A.A. *The Status of Women in Modern Russia: A General Overview*. – M., 2000.

Opening speech of Senate Chairwoman T. Narbaeva at the Asian Women's Forum.

Stat.edu.uz